

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron (III) with 1-Hydroxyxanthone

Brahm Dev and B. D. Jain

1-Hydroxyxanthone has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of iron (III). With iron (III) this reagent forms a yellowish green complex, soluble in 50% ethanol (v/v). The complex has been studied spectrophotometrically and its molar composition determined. The complex obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 425 m μ within the concentration range 1.1-11.0 p.p.m. of iron. The intensity of the colour does not vary between pH 1.8 and 2.3. The molar composition of iron (III)—1-hydroxyxanthone shows that it contains iron and the xanthone in the molar ratio of 1:2. The limits of interference due to various cations and anions in the determination have been given.

Ferron¹, salicylic acid², sulphosalicylic acid³, thioglycollic acid⁴, disodium 1,2-dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonate⁵, and potassium thiocyanate are generally used for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric iron. In the case of thiocyanate method, a large excess of the reagent is necessary for complete colour development and the reagent can be used only within a limited pH range. The colour of the complex formed also fades rapidly with time⁶.

1-Hydroxyxanthone has been used for the determination of uranium and thorium and for their separation from rare earths as well as for the gravimetric determination of cerium(IV) and its separation from other rare earths⁷.

During the course of our investigation on 1-hydroxyxanthone as an analytical reagent⁷, we find that it may be used advantageously for the spectrophotometric determination of iron in the ferric state, whereas Fe(II) exhibits with this reagent a greenish tinge which is too faint for spectrophotometric investigations. Fe(III) forms a yellowish green complex, which is soluble in aqueous ethanol and obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 425 m μ in the concentration range 1.1-11.0 p.p.m. of iron. The intensity of its colour does not vary between pH 1.8 and 2.3.

1. Yoe and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 872.
2. Gregory, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 93; Mehlig, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1938, **10**, 136; Scott, *Analyst*, 1941, **66**, 142.
3. Lorber, *Biochem. Z.*, 1927, **181**, 391.
4. Swank and Mellon, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1938, **10**, 7.
5. Yoe and Jones, *ibid.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
6. Snell and Snell, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", Vol. II, 3rd ed., Van Nostrand, New York, 1954, p. 307.
7. Dev and Jain, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1961, **54A**, 341; *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 457.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Hydroxyxanthone, prepared as outlined previously⁷, was further purified by passing through alumina column. This material (53 mg.) was dissolved in ethanol and the final volume made to 250 ml; with ethanol, the strength of the solution so obtained was 1×10^{-3} mole/litre. Ferric perchlorate solution (*pH* 1) containing 10^{-3} mole/litre was employed as a standard solution for iron.

Spectrophotometric measurements over a range of 400-700 $m\mu$ were made with a Unicam spectrophotometer, model S. P. 600. Absorption cells used were 1 cm thick.

A Beckman *pH* meter, Model H2, with a suitable glass electrode was used for measuring *pH*.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectrum of 1-hydroxyxanthone was taken in the visible region and the maximum absorption was observed at 380 $m\mu$. The absorption spectrum of Fe(III)—1 hydroxyxanthone showed no sharp maximum in the visible region. A strong absorption at 425 $m\mu$ was, however, observed and a maximum of low intensity at 580 $m\mu$ was also recorded. All subsequent spectrophotometric studies of the complex were carried out at 425 $m\mu$, as the absorption due to the reagent was quite negligible at this wave length.

Absorption spectra of the complex were taken at *pH* between 1.0 and 6.0; 0.1*N*. NaOH was used for adjustment of *pH*. The complex at *pH* 1.0 to 2.5 exhibited maximum absorption at 415-425 $m\mu$ and also at 575-580 $m\mu$. At higher *pH*, the complex showed maximum absorption at 420-425 $m\mu$ only.

Minimum Amount of the Reagent Necessary for Determination of Fe(III).—The optical density at 425 $m\mu$ of a series of solutions containing 1-hydroxyxanthone and Fe(III) in the molar ratios of 0.5:1 to 9:1 was determined. The results (Fig. 1) show that the curve is a straight line up to the molar ratio of 5. The molar ratio of the reagent to iron was maintained at 10 in subsequent estimations. An excess of the reagent did not affect the optical density of the complex.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Effect of pH on Fe (III)—1-hydroxyxanthone Complex.—The effect of pH on the complex was studied and it was found that the absorption by the complex remained the same in the pH range 1.8-2.3 (Fig. 2). The pH of Fe(III) solution was adjusted with 0.1N-NaOH or 0.1N-HCl.

Stability of the Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the complex was found to be stable and no change in the optical density was observed after keeping the complex for 6 hrs. The complex was found to obey Lambert-Beer's law at 425 m μ for the concentration range of 1.1-11.0 p.p.m. of iron.

Molar Composition of the Complex.—The molar composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continued variations⁸ as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁹ at 425 m μ employing concentrations of (a) 1.0×10^{-3} M and (b) 0.5×10^{-3} M. The values of y (optical density) are plotted against x in case of both concentrations in Fig. 3 and the peaks occur when the molar ratio of the xanthone to Fe(III) ions is 6.5:3.5, i.e. 2:1 (~) in each case. The complex therefore has the molar composition FeM_2 where M is xanthone molecule.

FIG. 3

(x litres of N -molar of the reagent added to $(1-x)$ litres of N -molar Fe(III) soln.)

8. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **2**, 9, 113.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—The interference due to various ions in the determination of Fe(III) with the reagent was investigated and it was found that sulphate, oxalate, tartrate, citrate, fluoride, phosphate, zirconium, titanium, beryllium, copper, lead, and aluminium ions interfere even in minute quantities. The limits of interference due to the following ions were determined per 5.5 p.p.m. of iron: chloride (200 times), iodide (8 times), bromide (10 times), sulphocyanide (2 times), acetate (20 times), borate (25 times), nickel (40 times), cobalt (8 times), manganese (40 times), vanadium (10 times), tungsten (4 times).

The authors are grateful to Prof. T. R. Seshadri, F.R.S., Head of the Department, for his keen interest and helpful discussions.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY OF DELHI, DELHI 6.

Received November 13, 1961.